

THE IMPORTANCE OF FORMING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF NEW GENERATION PEDAGOGUES.

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Annotation: The formation of a person who fully meets the requirements of the society, a competitive production sector, capable of adapting to abrupt changes, as well as effectively acting at the level of qualification requirements in the labor market is one of the urgent tasks nowadays. The study of professional competencies in teaching future teachers is described in this article.

Key words: Professional competence, competence, communication, Education,

Professional competence of the future teacher, willpower qualities, intellectual potential, emotional qualities, practical skills, self based on the interdependence of management abilities and individual qualities that reflect the level of socio-cultural activity of the individual formed.

Professional qualification in accordance with the tradition formed in European countries the competence of the specialist, the education aimed at shaping it and the system is measured by the level of knowledge, skills and abilities.

Important pedagogical conditions in the preparation of a future teacher The following can be recognized as:

- normative and educational-methodical that can meet modern requirements documents (state educational standard, standard curricula, working training plans,

sample curricula, work programs, textbooks, curriculum manuals, methodical recommendations, additional special literature, instructions availability of tools, lesson plans, projects, etc.);

- Scientific and pedagogical staff (professors, associate professors, teachers, qualified knowledge, skills and competencies of training masters, technical staff) high, sufficiently formed level of professional competence and have scientific potential;

The competence of the specialist should include issues related to overcoming production and interpersonal conflict situations. The ability of a person to establish and effectively implement interpersonal contacts seems to be an important condition for achieving success in professional activity and adaptation in the work team. In the structure of such competence, three main levels can be distinguished, each of which includes components:

- 1) cognitive level (knowledge and creative components);
- 2) motivational level (motivational-need component and component of personal characteristics);
- 3) the regulatory level (emotional, volitional and communicative components).

The competency-based approach to organizing the educational process by a university, developed today by many researchers, opens up fundamentally new pedagogical opportunities in solving the problem of improving the quality of training of specialists. Essential in this approach is the refusal to focus mainly on the subject preparation of a future specialist. One of the most promising pedagogical technologies that implement the basic ideas of a comprehensive approach is the technology of profiling teaching courses. The pedagogical essence of the profiling of teaching university courses is revealed by the corresponding system of principles, which also includes the following:

- the principle of complexity - work on profiling the course should cover all the relationships of this course with the relevant subjects of the curriculum;

- the principle of integrity - profiling the course should not violate its logical harmony and scientific integrity;
- principle of scientific relevance - the content of leading topics should as much as possible meet the achievements of the relevant fields of science;
- The principle of priority of applied tasks - in training sessions, first of all, applied problems should be offered for solving, which have a very definite value in terms of the formation of individual components of the corresponding competence.

The competency model consists of a number of blocks (for example, analytics, self-management, performing skills and interpersonal skills) and constitutes a competency cluster implemented using the Balanced Score Card. All of these blocks reflect the systemic opposites of internal and external influences.

Competencies are only a part, one of the four elements of the personnel management system that cannot replace the other three: corporate culture, organizational order and business procedures for personnel management. However, only in combination do these four elements provide the personnel management system with the maximum effect and effectiveness in implementing the strategy and achieving goals.

Any of the clusters of competencies can be considered as a management process that includes an object, a subject and the relationship between them in the form of motivation and joint actions. Without the strong support of the leadership of the university, this very immature competency-based approach cannot be mechanically integrated into the tradition of explanatory and illustrative teaching that has deep historical roots. There are fears that he might be absorbed in this tradition, since more than once or twice has happened - it is enough to recall the programmed training or the experience of innovative teachers. In this case, the loss of the educational system can become irreparable.

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